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Society's material stocks as carbon pool: an economy-wide quantification of global carbon stocks from 1900–2015

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Society's material stocks as carbon pool: an economy-wide quantification of global carbon stocks from 1900–2015

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E-mail: lisa.kaufmann@boku.ac.at**Keywords:** carbon stock, global carbon cycle, carbon accountingSupplementary material for this article is available [online](#)**Abstract**

Societal activities massively alter the global carbon (C) cycle, thereby driving global climate heating. Socioeconomic material stocks - e.g. in buildings and infrastructures - have been identified as a C pool that can potentially store increasing amounts of C, thereby keeping C away from the atmosphere. However, little is known about the size, composition, distribution and development of global socioeconomic C stocks. Based on an established economy-wide C accounting approach from sociometabolic research, we consistently and comprehensively quantified the C contained in eight components of socioeconomic stocks in the period 1900–2015 at the level of nine world regions. We discern inert (aggregates and other gravel) and 'active' climate-relevant (i.e. biomass and fossil-fuel based) C pools. We find that global active components of socioeconomic C stocks grew by a factor of 9, from 1.9 (1.5–2.2) Pg of carbon (PgC) to 16.8 (13.7–20.2) PgC. The inert socioeconomic C stock in aggregates & other gravel amounted to 25.2 (6.1–48.0) PgC in 2015, however with high uncertainties. Absolute annual net additions to stock (NAS) of active stock components was 0.49 (0.40–0.59) PgC yr⁻¹ which equaled 5% of the C emissions from fossil fuel combustion and industrial processes. However, raising NAS of components with biomass feedstock that sequester C from the atmosphere comes with biodiversity and food security trade-offs. This study contributes to a holistic perspective on social and natural C stocks that acknowledges their interactions. The global socioeconomic C stock reached a geologically relevant extent (approximately the size of C in coasts) and should therefore be integrated in the assessments of the global C cycle to acknowledge the Anthropocene.

1. Introduction

Potentials for enhancing carbon (C) sinks in social and natural systems are an increasingly debated topic in climate science and policy. Storing C in social and natural systems prevents C emissions to the atmosphere or even remove C from the atmosphere, thus reducing future temperature increases. Therefore, C storage has become a crucial element of climate change mitigation [1–3]. For example, Desing [4] estimated that ~400 Pg of C

(PgC, 1 Pg = 10¹⁵ g = 1 Gt) has to be removed from the atmosphere to achieve pathways compatible with the 'Paris Goal' of limiting climate heating to 1.5° above preindustrial global temperatures until 2100.

While C sinks in (natural and human-modified respectively managed) ecosystems have received considerable attention [5–7], a growing body of literature has started to explore whether the growth of socioeconomic C stocks could act as substantial C sink [8, 9]. Studies estimate that humanity has accumulated ~1064 Gt of materials in stocks of buildings,

infrastructure, and machinery globally [10, 11]. Since ~2020, socioeconomic material stocks even surpass the weight (dry-matter) of all living biomass [12].

Several studies suggest using biomass-based products to store atmospheric C [13–15]. Especially timber for construction is increasingly discussed, partly because production of wood-based elements is associated with smaller greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions than steel or concrete, but also because construction timber can act as medium- to long-term C storage [16]. Concrete sequesters C during the lifetime of concrete stocks and in the end-of-life waste management phase ('carbonation') [14, 17, 18]. A circular bio-based plastics sector has been assessed as potential C sink [19], leading Suh and Bradow [20] to suggest that societal material stocks in what they call the 'technosphere' can be conceptualized as distinct Earth system compartment storing C and thereby contributing to mitigating climate heating.

So far, studies estimating the potentials of socioeconomic C stocks for climate-change mitigation mostly focused either on specific materials or sectors, with only one study attempting to create a comprehensive estimate. For example, Johnston and Radeloff [21] estimated via open-access data from the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations that in 2015 4.8 PgC was stored globally in harvested wood products (HWP) and annually stored C was less than 1% of global emissions. Zhang et al [22] obtained an in-use HWP C stock of 2.9 PgC based on multiregional input–output tables from the EORA database. Churkina [23] estimated that the urban land C pool in buildings (6.7 PgC) and landfills (30 PgC), while including the uptake of C of concrete, accounted for 1.6% of total vegetation and soil pools. Cote et al [24] modeled C stocks and flows associated to the pulp and paper industry in Germany obtaining a stock of 34 TgC in 2010. Churkina et al [9] assessed the global GHG mitigation potential of substituting steel and concrete with engineered timber structures and concluded that C pools in buildings could have advantages in comparison to 'other engineered carbon sinks'. Cao et al [17] compiled current and future global net C balances between production emissions of cement and carbonation of concrete for the years 2015–2100 showing that up to 30% of cumulative CO₂ emissions could be reabsorbed. Stegmann et al [19] estimated a global in-use plastic stock of 3.03 Gt in 2015 and scrutinized future mitigation potentials of plastic in a circular bioeconomy. To our knowledge, only Lauk et al [25] estimated global socioeconomic C stocks for the period 1900–2008 in cereals, plastics, bitumen, and wood products, as well as C contained in the human and livestock population, however without any regional differentiation. Furthermore, the study did not include C in concrete from carbonation and inorganic C in aggregates and other gravel. Therefore, a comprehensive, up-to-date

economy-wide characterization of the size and development of socioeconomic C stocks on global and regional scales is missing.

Herein, we comprehensively quantify the amount of C in socioeconomic stocks from 1900 to 2015. This includes C in infrastructure, buildings and other products comprising aggregates and other gravel, solid wood products, concrete, bitumen, plastics, paper, agricultural products, steel as well as livestock and human population across nine world-regions. Based on our empirical data, our aim is to answer the following research questions: *how did the size and composition of socioeconomic C stocks develop across the world in the last century? How are these C stocks distributed globally? Did past C stock accumulation contribute to climate change mitigation?* Further, based on our results, we like to discuss which socioeconomic C stocks are relevant for the global C cycle and climate change mitigation, and if and how socioeconomic C stocks could become more relevant.

2. Method and data

To quantify socioeconomic C stocks, we used an established system definition derived from sociometabolic research [26], more specifically, economy-wide material and energy flow analysis that also has been used for economy-wide C accounting [27]. According to this approach, the socioeconomic system comprises the material stocks in buildings, infrastructure, machinery and other products, livestock and the human population (figure 1(a)). In accordance with this definition, we excluded landfills and unmanaged waste deposits, as flows of wastes to a deposit are treated as outflows of the socioeconomic system in this convention [26]. Since our focus is on stocks, we did not consider C fluxes from extraction or combustion of fossil energy carriers and, due to lacking data, we also excluded C pools from storage of fossil fuels (e.g. in tanks).

We assembled stock data on human population and livestock species [28–31], material stocks in buildings, infrastructure and machinery [11, 32], and stocks of stored agricultural products [33]. We further compiled a dataset on C contents (α) of livestock and human population, of seven different components of socioeconomic material stocks and of agricultural products (k), see table 1, that we multiplied with data on the mass of socioeconomic stocks (S) to obtain socioeconomic C stocks (C) for each region (r) and year (y).

$$C_{k,r,y} = S_{k,r,y} * \alpha_{k,r}$$

Additionally, we quantified the continuous inflow of C ('carbonation') into in-use stocks of concrete and the resulting build-up of C stocks in concrete, and estimated the reduction of C stocks in bitumen

Table 1. C content, additional descriptions and comments and references of all 8 C stock components and human and livestock population.

Stock component	Additional description	C content in %	Additional comments	References
Aggregates and other gravel	Crushed stones and gravels used in construction (asphalt, concrete, sub-base of built structures)	3 (0.2–5.7)	62 (57–68)% coarse aggregates 42 (3–70)% limestone 12% carbon	[34–40]
Solid wood products	For construction, manufacturing and other uses	48 (45–50)	(1) Conversion from air dry weight (15%) from MISO results to oven dry (0%) (2) Region-specific average weighted according to apparent consumption of sawn wood (50%) and wood-based panels (45%)	[41]
Concrete	Carbonation of buildings and infrastructure		Explained in section 2.2	
Bitumen	Binder in asphalt for road pavement	85 (82–88)	VOC off-gassing: $-0.4\% \text{ yr}^{-1}$ for the top 0.5 cm layer in road pavements affecting 10.5% of asphalt stocks	[42, 43]
Plastics	Various polymers, synthetic fibers and additives commonly used	76	Weighted average considering plastic types (HDPE, PVC, ...) in production	[44–46]
Paper		39		[41]
Agricultural products	Storage at the end of the year (e.g. corn)	50	Conversion to dry matter with crop-specific factors	
Steel		0.4		[9]
Human population		50	Conversion to dry matter assuming 70% water content	[47]
Livestock		50	Conversion to dry matter assuming 70% water content	[47]

due to outgassing induced by temperature and sunlight exposure (figure 1(b)). Annual net additions to stocks (NAS) of C are calculated from the difference between stocks of consecutive years. In other words, we calculated the first derivative of year-to-year changes (dC/dt) to approximate net changes of socioeconomic C stocks.

$$\text{NAS}_{k,r,y} = C_{k,r,y} - C_{k,r,y-1}.$$

In total, eight major C stock components in artifacts (aggregates and other gravel, solid wood products, concrete, bitumen, plastics, paper, agricultural products, steel) were considered along with C in human and livestock populations.

2.1. Socio-economic material stocks

Material stock data of buildings, infrastructure and machinery were sourced from an economy-wide dynamic material flow accounting (MFA) model (MISO model v1) [11, 32]. MISO-v1 calculates material stocks from inflows, outflows, recycling, downcycling and residual final waste, for nine world regions from 1900 to 2015 for 14 bulk materials. For all details, we refer to the original publications [11, 32]. We followed the geographical resolution from this study (for countries included in world regions see SI) and utilized stock estimates for asphalt, concrete, downcycled construction minerals, primary sand and gravel, solid wood products, plastics, papers, and steel. For bricks, aluminum, copper, all other metals, flat glass, and container glass, we assumed zero C content [48, 49].

We combined all aggregates and other gravel from asphalt, concrete, downcycled materials and primary sand and gravel, with an asphalt composition of 95% aggregates and 5% bitumen [50] and a concrete composition of 83% aggregates and 17% cement [51]. Downcycled materials were separated into bricks, asphalt, and concrete with the same C content as the primary material (except for asphalt outgassing and concrete carbonation). We only considered coarse aggregates as source of C (62% of total aggregates based on average concrete mixtures [34, 35]) and assumed zero C for fine aggregates (primarily sand). Because extraction and material composition of mined aggregates is very poorly reported [50, 52], we only considered the main C-containing mineral, that is limestone. Limestone's share in excavated aggregates varies by region, and data are only available for a few countries (e.g. USA, China). Hence, we assumed the average of available data as best guess (table 1), but included minimal and maximum values in the uncertainty assessment (see SI for more explanations). Aggregate C in non-metallic minerals such as limestone is inorganically bound and does not significantly affect the climate-relevant C cycle. Therefore, we report 'inert' C in minerals and 'active' C in other

components (e.g. wood, plastics) potentially impacting the global C cycle in the short-term, separately (see SI for further details).

Agricultural biomass stocks are products that are stored for longer than a year (e.g. corn) of which we accounted for 48 different products [33]. Data from 1961 to 2015 were converted to dry matter using crop-specific factors [31]. Data prior to 1961 were extrapolated using the stock/population ratio in 1961. To account for year-to-year variability, a three-year average in a given year was used [25].

2.2. C sequestration of concrete and degradation of asphalt C stocks

We employed a physicochemical model to quantify C sequestered by in-use cement stocks ('carbonation') [17, 53, 54]. The model considers various factors, such as the thicknesses of distinct cement-related materials, exposure conditions across various strength classes, and atmospheric CO₂ concentrations in different geographic regions. To align with the dynamic MFA model, we incorporated a survival function into the model [55, 56], as opposed to using an average lifetime [53]. This allowed us to capture the survival probability of a collective set of buildings and infrastructures [57, 58], providing more robust means. C sequestration by concrete and mortar is contingent upon the carbonation rate, CaO content, the proportion of CaO that transforms into CaCO₃ (at complete carbonation), and the mole ratio of CO₂ to CaO. Carbonation rates were modeled using Fick's diffusion law, adjusted based on factors like exposed surface area, thickness, compressive strength class, exposure condition, cement additives, atmospheric CO₂ concentration, coatings, coverings, and exposure duration. More details about the model can be found in previous studies [17, 59].

Asphalt surfaces are affected by solar radiation and high temperatures, leading to emissions of volatile organic compounds (VOCs, 'out-gassing') [60, 61]. We modeled asphalt C stock degradation at 0.4% per year for the top 0.5 cm layer in road pavements [43], impacting 10.5% of asphalt stocks (see SI), and reduced annual asphalt C stocks accordingly.

2.3. Livestock and human population

To estimate C in livestock, we used FAO data on 16 livestock species from 1961 to 2015 [29, 30]. Values before 1961 were linearly interpolated from data pertaining to 1910, 1930, and 1950 [31], and values from 1900 to 1910 extrapolated based on human population changes [28]. We multiplied livestock numbers by species-specific mass per animal [47] and human population by a global average body mass of 54.9 kg derived from gender and age specific body weights for the year 2000 (more details in Lauk *et al* [25]). Both were converted to dry matter, assuming 70% water content [47].

Figure 2. Global socioeconomic C stocks (a) by component from 1900 to 2015 and the share of C in total socioeconomic stocks (sec. axis); (b) by component in 2015 incl. error bars; (c) uncertainty range from 1900 to 2015. We refer to C in aggregates and other gravel as ‘inert’ C, while the remaining categories are classified as ‘active’ (relevant to climate change mitigation).

3. Results

3.1. The size and composition of the socio-economic C stock from 1900 to 2015

Global socioeconomic C stock grew from 2.5 (1.5–3.7) PgC in 1900 to 42.0 (19.8–68.2) PgC in 2015, a 17-fold increase (figure 2(a)). The C content of total socioeconomic stocks decreased from 5.9% to 3.9% due to changes in size and composition of material stocks (i.e. more minerals, less biomass). Inert C in aggregates and gravel dominated this growth, growing from 0.6 (0.1–1.5) PgC in 1900 (23.9%; 4.0%–40.7% of total) to 25.2 (6.1–48.0) PgC in 2015 (59.9% of total; 30.7%–70.4%), with significant uncertainty (figures 2(b) and (c)).

In 1900, active C stocks accounted for 76.1% (59.3%–96.0%) of socioeconomic C stocks; a value that dropped to 41.1% (29.9%–69.3%) in 2015. C in solid wood products increased from 1.8 (1.4–2.1) PgC (71.9%; 56.1%–90.3%) to 6.9 (5.6–8.3) PgC during the study period, while its share of total C stock decreased to 16.5% (12.1%–28.3%). In 2015, bitumen stocks contained 3.4 (2.9–3.9) PgC, which equals 8.1% (5.7%–14.8%) of all C stocks. C outgassing reduced bitumen C stocks only by 0.04%. For plastics, we estimated a stock of 3.0 (2.4–3.5) PgC; i.e. 6.9% (5.1%–12.1%) of total C stocks. Concrete C from carbonation reached 2.7 (2.1–3.6) PgC in 2015, representing 6.5% (5.2%–10.7%) of the total. Paper, agricultural products, steel, and human and livestock populations amounted to 0.8 (0.7–1.0) PgC, which was 2.0% (1.4%–3.5%) of total C stocks in 2015.

3.2. Patterns of C stocks in world regions

In 1900, C shares in socioeconomic stocks varied widely by region, from 2.2% in India to 16.5% in industrial new world (figure 3(a)). Toward 1990, C shares converged to 3%–5% across regions. High C shares were observed in early and wood stock-building regions in the new industrial world and in the former Soviet Union (FSU). However, by the end of the 20th century, and similar to the global average,

limestone C in aggregates and other gravel, concrete and asphalt dominated C stocks in all regions.

In 2015, global ‘active’ socioeconomic C stocks were 16.8 (13.7–20.2) PgC, showing a nine-fold increase, from 1.9 (1.5–2.2) PgC in 1900 (figure 3(b)). Contrary to total socioeconomic stocks, in 1900, the majority of active C stocks resided in the industrial new world with a value of 0.9 (0.7–1.0) PgC (48%). Only by 1980, the industrial old world’s C stocks exceeded the industrial new world, reaching 4.9 (4.0–5.8) PgC in 2015. Together with the FSU, these three regions held almost 89% of all socioeconomic C stocks in 1900. The FSU began the 20th century with 0.35 (0.27–0.41) PgC, constituting 19% of global active C stocks, which grew 1.89 (1.48–2.33) PgC or 11% of global C stocks by 2015. China’s C stocks increased from 0.11 (0.09–0.13) PgC in 1900 to 2.7 (2.2–3.4) PgC in 2015, representing 16% of global active C stocks in 2015. The five other world regions together started at 0.09 (0.08–0.11) PgC in 1900, equivalent to 5%, and reached 21% (3.5; 2.9–4.2 PgC) in 2015.

3.3. Growth of socio-economic C stocks

Annual net growth (=NAS) rose from 26.4 (14.7–41.6) TgC yr⁻¹ in 1900 to 1367 (839–1993) TgC yr⁻¹ in 2015 (figure 4(a)). Total NAS, however, was dominated by inert C in aggregates and other gravel with high uncertainty and limited relevance for climate heating. In 1900, solid wood products contributed the most to active carbon growth with 14.5 (11.8–16.2) TgC yr⁻¹ (figure 4(b)). It continued to be the primary source of climate-relevant (active) C for stock growth until 1990, but was later surpassed by C in bitumen, plastics and concrete. In 2013, NAS in solid wood products returned to their 1990 levels. In 2015, plastics were the largest contributor to NAS (after inert C). Their accumulation started around 1960 and reached 135 (111–159) Mt C⁻¹ in 2015. The dynamics of concrete C resembled that of plastic C with a very similar NAS of 133 (101–175) TgC yr⁻¹ in 2015. NAS in paper and agricultural products showed

Figure 3. (a) Shares of C in total socioeconomic stocks in each region; (b) active global socioeconomic stock by region with values indicated on the right; from 1900 to 2015 (active = all but inert C in aggregates).

Figure 4. Carbon stocks growth in net additions to stocks (NAS) per year: (a) all components and total, (b) active components, (c) all components by world region, (d) active components by world region. (Please mind the varying limits on the y-axis).

a high year-to-year fluctuation. C in steel experienced growth from 0.2 TgC yr^{-1} in 1901 to 3.5 TgC yr^{-1} in 2015. The growth of the human population and livestock herds resulted in moderate NAS, averaging 0.6 TgC yr^{-1} .

In 2002, China surpassed all other regions in NAS for all components, and in 2008, it did the same for active carbon components (figures 4(c) and (d)). By 2015, China's NAS had grown to 717 (595–849) TgC yr^{-1} and 216 (178–264) TgC yr^{-1} , for all and active components, respectively. The highest annual growth for active components in the industrial old and new world occurred in 2006 at 105 (86–121) TgC yr^{-1} and in 2004 at 87 (73–98) TgC yr^{-1} , respectively. Only FSU countries experienced a reduction of socioeconomic C stocks with negative NAS

(decrease) of 16.4 (7–17) TgC yr^{-1} for active components from 1993 to 2006 and again between 2009 and 2010.

4. Discussion

Almost two thirds of the $\sim 42 \text{ PgC}$ of socioeconomic C stocks in 2015 are mostly inert with minimal short to medium-term interaction with the global C cycle. Our estimate of 'active' C in socioeconomic stocks accumulating from 1900 to 2015 was 16.8 PgC , equivalent to 4% of the C removal required for a $1.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ pathway until 2100 according to Desing [4]. In 2015, NAS was 491 TgC yr^{-1} , roughly 5% of emissions from fossil fuel combustion and industrial processes

[62]. While certainly not negligible, this flow is currently insufficient to offset the emissions driving climate heating (even with 45% C likely from fossil sources). Notably, C stocks increased less (factor 17 between 1900 and 2015) than total socioeconomic stocks (factor 25), with the active component growing even less (factor 9).

Our interpretation of inorganic C as ‘inert’ must be taken with a grain of salt since inorganic C can play a role in the C cycle over longer time periods. The contribution of these materials to C stocks growth results from a relocation from natural deposits into what is defined as the socioeconomic system in sociometabolic research. Moreover, scarce and deviant data, particularly in the construction sector, result in a particularly high uncertainty.

4.1. Comparison with other studies

Lauk *et al* [25] reported a global socioeconomic C stock of 11.5 PgC in 2008. Our estimate for the same year and components is in good agreement at 11.9 PgC, while our work includes additional components and enables regional differentiation. Huang *et al* [18] reported a concrete carbonation uptake of 22.9 Gt CO₂ until 2021, equivalent to 4.2 PgC in use until 2015, while our estimate of 2.7 PgC is 36% lower but still within the uncertainty range (2.3–4.9 PgC). For plastics, Stegmann *et al* [19] found a global in-use stock of 3.03 Gt in 2015, 28% higher than our estimate. Due to its relevance as C storage, more studies on wood C stocks exist, albeit with great methodological variations. We roughly compared solid wood and paper product results using EORA multiregional input–output tables for 1992–2015 [22]. For this period and materials, we estimated a global C stock of 1.4 PgC, 49% of their estimate (2.9 PgC). In contrast, the global stock of HWP estimated by Johnston and Radeloff [21] was 4.8 PgC, and hence only 66% of our estimate until 2015. Uncertainty in solid wood products arises from the methodological approach for estimating material stocks, which is discussed elsewhere [11, 32]—rather than C content. The main source of uncertainty in this study is C in aggregates due to limited data availability for mining construction material and mineralogical–petrographic composition [50, 52], with no comparable studies available.

4.2. Socio-economic C stocks and mitigation of climate heating

Socio-economic C stocks can contribute to climate-change mitigation by keeping C from the atmosphere. This can be achieved either by extending the residence time of biotic C in non-atmospheric pools (as in the use of long-lived wood products), or by directly sequestering atmospheric C (as in carbonation). At approximately 7 PgC in 2015, wood products contribute 17% to total socioeconomic C stocks and 41% of active socioeconomic C stock

components, i.e. the largest C share of the latter. This amount equals ca. 1.5% of global biomass stocks in ecosystems [63]. Because wood in construction may store C for a significant amount of time and, in addition, may replace other emission-intensive materials such as steel and concrete, enthusiasm has recently surged among scholars and practitioners alike creating the ‘theory of buildings as a C sink’ [9, 13, 14, 64]. Assessing the C storage in socioeconomic wood stocks has resulted in a wide range of assessments due to variations in accounting methods: a recent review reported cumulative C storage in buildings and construction products ranging from zero to 175% of fossil fuel emissions in one year [13]. Johnston and Radeloff [21] found that C stored in HWPs annually mitigated less than 1% of global anthropogenic CO₂ emissions and that unforeseen economic shocks resulted in negative additions of C in HWPs, as observed after the collapse of the Soviet Union (after 1990) and the 2008–2009 economic crisis. Therefore, they argue that C accumulation in HWPs can only play a minor role in climate-change mitigation. Scenarios for increasing wood in construction in the next decades estimate NAS in buildings to range from 10 to 680 TgC yr⁻¹ in 2020–2050 [9], and from 32 to 243 TgC yr⁻¹ in 2020–2100 [8] depending on the scenario assumptions. These numbers amount to 0.1–6.4 times the NAS of all wood products (not only construction) in 2015 according to our results. Incorporating more wood into socioeconomic C stocks however requires either large-scale expansion of tree plantations or intensification of forest use. The effect of such options is under debate, with some scholars arguing that increased wood demand might enhance more effective forest management [65], while others warn that increasing harvest could undermine the ecological integrity of forests and their capacity to act as C sinks [66, 67]. Either way, the climate-change mitigation effect of C accumulation in socioeconomic timber stocks is constrained by biological capacities of ecosystems, because harvesting more than the annual woody increment reduces ecosystem C pools and thus does not contribute to keeping C from the atmosphere. As an alternative, agricultural by-products (e.g. straw) are currently being discussed as a building material with high net C removal potential without additional land requirements [68, 69].

In 2015, NAS from plastics ranks second among all and first among active components. C in plastics is primarily sourced from fossil fuels (mainly petroleum oil) that is relocated C from the ground to the socioeconomic system. However, considerable C releases are related to this process: first, plastic production emits CO₂ amounting to 4.5% of total global greenhouse gas emissions [70] and, second, plastic disposal releases C to the atmosphere (e.g. incineration). Predictions of doubled or even tripled plastic production by 2050 or 2100 raise concerns

[19]. One scenario results in even negative emissions by sequestering C in bio-based plastics and improving circularity [19]. However, a rough estimate suggests this approach would require 89 million hectares of land, approximately twice the size of California, including trade-offs with other environmental impacts and in particular food security. Consequently, increasing C stocks in plastics may lead to unintended consequences with both primary feedstocks.

Bituminous binders used in road pavements originate from fossil fuels, specifically petroleum. The C in bitumen is thus shifted from stable deposits to potentially less stable socioeconomic stocks. The exposure of surface bitumen to oxygen and sunlight can initiate oxidation that releases C in VOCs, impacting health and climate adversely. An elemental analysis showed a 2% reduction of C stocks over 5 years [43], indicating a relatively minor C release. Even at the end of asphalt's life, bitumen C is largely retained during re- or downcycling or landfilling. Due to potential depletion of fossil oil, there is interest in replacing it with renewable sources like vegetable oil [71], which, like plastics, could be used to argue negative emissions. However, this approach may have trade-offs related to land use, biodiversity, forest conservation, and food security.

Carbonation of concrete added nearly equal amounts of C to the socioeconomic C stock as plastic in 2015. Hydrated cement in concrete absorbs CO₂ via carbonation of calcium oxide [17, 18, 54]. We estimated a C stock of 2.7 PgC in 2015, equivalent to 10.0 PgCO₂ removed from the atmosphere since 1900. Other estimates obtained an offset of 55.1% of cumulative process emissions from cement production between 1930 and 2021 [18]. Projections suggest a 30% offset from 2015 to 2100 [17]. Thus, while concrete absorbs C from the atmosphere, the 'sponge effect' does not significantly contribute to climate change mitigation, offsetting only a fraction of historical cement production emissions.

5. Conclusion

Our analysis of the size, distribution and development of socioeconomic C stocks from 1900 to 2015 shows a substantial growth of global socioeconomic C stocks. The current size of this stock is comparable to other pools of the global C cycle (C in coasts) and C in- and outflows connect these pools. Hence, its integration into global C accounting would acknowledge the current period of the Anthropocene. We show that the annual accumulation of active C stocks (even partly from fossil sources), while not negligible, makes up for a minor fraction of annual emissions, and its potential for climate-change mitigation is limited. The relative relevance of wood, the component with the highest C-storage potential, decreased

during the studied period. To get a more conclusive understanding about climate-change mitigation potentials of socioeconomic C stock accumulation, it will be crucial to integrate our results into an even more holistic perspective that takes natural C stocks, in particular of forests, into consideration, as well as trade-offs to e.g. food security and biodiversity.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available upon request from the authors.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interest.

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